

Comparative Analysis of Diseases Discovered among Blood Donors: An Experimental Design Study Conducted in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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More Information

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Abstract

The study made a comparative Analysis of the diseases discovered among donors in the process of blood donation using Greaco-Latin square. This is done to determine whether significant differences exist between the different factors considered in the study such as: age groups, period, hospitals and diseases discovered among blood donors. Analysis of variance using 4x4 Greaco-Latin square experimental design was used to design and analyze the data collected on age groups, period, hospitals and diseases from the design to make comparison using MINITAB software for the analysis of the collected data. Results obtained from the analysis, showed that for the four hypotheses tested for the main effects of the four factors included in the study, it was discovered that the test for the first and third factors i.e. months and hospitals were accepted as the P value obtained is greater than the alpha value while for the other two factors i.e. age groups and diseases, the hypotheses were all rejected as the P value obtained is less than the alpha value at 5% level of significance. It is therefore concluded that effects due to months and hospitals are not significant while effects due to age groups and diseases are significant at 5% level of significance. In the same vein General hospital Zauro has the highest mean values among hospitals while syphilis has the highest mean among the diseases.

Introduction

Blood donation is an essential concern for the society, as it saves life of patients with bleeding disorders, surgeries, inherited/acquired hematological diseases, accidents and malignancies (National blood policy). According to [1], the voluntary and non remunerated blood donors are cornerstone of a safe adequate supply of blood and blood components. [2] said the main challenges for any blood transfusion service, is recruiting voluntary blood donors.

In the developed world, most blood donors are voluntary. On their own, people go to blood banks to donate blood freely, which is World Health Organization (WHO) standard. Therefore, 100 per cent of blood donations in the developed world are done without money involved.

There are three types of blood donors: Voluntary donors are those that go to blood banks to donate blood free of charge. Then, there are family replacement blood donors, who go to hospital to

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donate blood because a family member, friend or neighbor who is sick and having shortage of blood. The third category is the commercial donors, who hang around hospitals to donate blood and collect money [3]. [3], also stated that one of the criteria in blood transfusion is age. Children are not advice to donate blood, as their blood volume is low. A potential donor should be between 18 and 60 years. The same applies to old people. She added that "Age is very essential because, as people aged, their cardiovascular systems are going down. This is why it is not advisable to donate blood at this stage. Again, it is unacceptable to donate more than 13 per cent of your blood volume. [4] indicated that 48.4% of the blood donors were in the age group of 26 to 50 years.

In a study by [5], blood donation was understood in a rational and evaluative manner by the majority of blood donors but in an emotional, personalized and stereotyped manner by minority. Continual donation as a form of help was rationalized as a function of internal and external factors notably personal convenience in comparison to other helping behaviors and ease of access to collection points.

[6], examined the interval between donations in group O, Rh negative blood donors by using survival analysis, they found that the likely hood of a subsequent donation attempt was associated with the interval between the first and second donations. The shorter the donation interval between the first two donations, the more likely the donor was to make subsequent donations. The proportion of repeat donors increased with education level. Rate of donation increased with age and education [7].

Recent studies evaluating the demographic characteristics of first time and return donors reveal that, those with a lower education level are less likely to donate blood than those with a higher educational level [7].

Methodology

This research is meant to study the diseases discovered among the donors in the process of blood donation. Four hospitals, four diseases, four age groups and period of four months were observed in this research. Unprocessed data on the number of donors with four different types of disease, their age groups and period of four months were collected from four separate hospitals mentioned below from daily register compiled by their respective laboratory technicians.

The hospitals are Sir Yahaya Memorial Hospital Birnin kebbi, General hospital juga, General hospital Zauru/Ambursa and General hospital Koko.

Hypothesis to be Tested

- 1. Ho: There is no significant difference between the four hospitals with respect to diseases
- H1: There is significant difference between the four hospitals with respect to diseases

2. Ho: There is no significant difference between the diseases and age groups

H1: There is significant difference between disease and age groups

3. Ho: There is no significant difference between the hospitals with respect to periods

H1: There is significant difference between the hospitals with respect to periods

4. Ho: There is no significant difference between the disease with respect to period across the four hospitals to be considered.

H1: There is significant difference between the diseases with respect to period across the four hospitals to be considered.

At 5% level of significant.

Graeco-Latin Square (Graeco-Latin Square)

The Graeco-Latin square (Graeco-Latin square) is an experimental design that superimposes one Latin square upon another. In this type of fractional factorial design, two sets of elements are arranged in the same set of cells in such a way that every row and every column contains each element of both sets once and once only, and each cell contains a different ordered pair. Graeco-Latin squares are used in research to minimize or eliminate the influence of extraneous variables and to balance order effects.

Mathematical model

The mathematical model for Graeco Latin square design is given by:

$$\bar{y}_{ijkl} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \Gamma_k + \theta_l + e_{ijkl} \tag{1}$$

i=1,2.....r

j=1,2.....r

k=1,2.....r

l=1,2.....r

where, y_{ijkl} = the response

μ =the overall mean

α_i =the i^{th} row effect (Period)

β_j =the j^{th} column effect (Age groups)

Γ_k =the k^{th} Latin letter effect

θ_l =the l^{th} greek letter effect

Graeco Latin Squares

A pair of orthogonal Latin squares, one with Latin symbols and the other with Greek symbols form a Graeco – Latin square.

Table 1: Example

A	α	B	β	C	γ	D	δ
B	δ	A	γ	D	β	C	α
C	β	D	α	A	δ	B	γ
D	γ	C	δ	B	α	A	β

Data presentation

Data on the number of disease, age group, hospitals and period respectively.

Table 2: Age Group

Period		16-25	26-35	36-45	46-60	Total
	August	A α 2	B β 13	C γ 42	D δ 41	98
	September	C δ 4	A γ 35	D β 2	B α 45	86
	October	D β 38	C α 0	B δ 33	A γ 50	121
	November	B γ 0	D δ 8	A α 32	C β 62	102
TOTAL	44	56	109	198	407	

A	B	C	D	Total
119	91	108	89	407

α	β	γ	δ	Total
88	99	177	43	407

Empirical Study

General Linear Model: Response versus Diseases, Age groups, Hospitals

Table 3: Between-Subjects Factors

Factor	Type	Level	Values
Months	Fixed	4	AUG, SEP, OCT, NOV
Age Group	Fixed	4	15-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-60
Hospitals	Fixed	4	SY, GZ, GJ, GK
Diseases	Fixed	4	HB, HC, HIV, SYP

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for Response, using Adjusted SS for Tests

Source	SS	DF	MS	F	P
Months	158.19	3	52.73	0.81	0.568
Age Group	3686.19	3	1228.73	18.80	0.019
Hospitals	153.69	3	43.92	0.67	0.624
Diseases	2305.77	3	769.59	11.76	0.036
Error	196.10	3	65.37		
Total	6499.94	15			

Note: S = 8.08505 R-Sq = 96.98% R-Sq (adj) = 84.91%

Figure 1: Main Effect Plot of Factors

Interpretation of Results

The data collected was arranged according to a Greco Latin square experimental design to test whether there are significance differences between the levels of all the four factors used in the study. Statistical software Package MINITAB windows was used to analyze the collected data and the results are presented in Table 4. Results obtained from the Greco Latin square design shows that the P- value obtained for the first factor i.e. Month is 0.568. At 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$, the P value is observed to be greater than the alpha value. On the basis of these results, the null hypothesis will be accepted meaning that effects due to the diseases are not significant.

Results obtained for the second factor i.e. Age group gave the P value as 0.019. At 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$, the P value is observed to be less than the alpha value. On the basis of these results, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning that effects due to age group are significant.

For the third factor i.e. hospital it can be observed that the P value was obtained as 0.642. At 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$, the P value is observed to be greater than the alpha value. On the basis of these results, the null hypothesis is accepted meaning that effects due to hospitals are not significant.

Similarly for the 4th factor i.e. disease it can be observed that the P value was obtained as 0.036. At 5% level of significance, i.e. $\alpha = 0.05$, the P value is observed to be less than the alpha value. On the basis of these results, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning that effects due to diseases are significant.

On the basis of the results obtained from the Greco Latin square design, it could be observed that for the four hypotheses tested for the main effects of the four factors included in the study, it was discovered that the test for the first and third factors i.e. months and hospitals were accepted while for the other two factors i.e. age group and diseases the hypotheses were all rejected at 5% level of significance. It can therefore be concluded that effects due to months and hospitals are not significant while effects due to age group and diseases are significant at 5%.

Figure 1 shows the main effect plot of the factors under study showing the fitted means for all the four factor levels for each of the 4 factors. As indicated on the graph it can be observed that the month of October has the highest mean among the months under study while the age group 46-60 has the highest among age groups. In the same vein General hospital Zauro has the highest mean values among hospitals while syphilis has the highest mean among the diseases.

Conclusion

Based on the research conducted the idea of donating blood is not bad, in fact it benefit the donor's self by reducing risk of heart disease, blood pressure & glucose.

Blood donation help in weight loss, those who are obese and are at higher risk of cardiovascular disease and other health disorder. On the basis of the results obtained from the Greco Latin square design, it could be observed that for the four hypotheses tested for the main effects of the four factors included in the study, it was discovered that the test for the first and third factors i.e. months and hospitals were accepted while for the other two factors i.e. age groups and diseases, the hypotheses were all rejected at 5% level of significance. It can therefore be concluded that effects due to months and hospitals are not significant while effects due to age groups and diseases are significant at 5%.

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